

Freedom of Speech and Expression in Militant-Affected Areas

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ABSTRACT

Roscoe Pound- *“Law is the product of an inexorable mechanism of social forces.”* After emerging from a grim battle against the British for recognition of the fundamental rights, the makers in the Constituent Assembly focussed on restrictions on freedom of speech and expression, as a means of safeguarding these rights in their pristine purity. The reason given was that there are persons in Society who can misuse those rights and may create anarchy. Hence limits were put on the operation of fundamental rights. Art. 19(1)(a) is limited in its scope by sub clause (2) as amended by the Constitution First Amendment Act (1951) with retrospective effect and (Sixteenth Amendment) Act, 1963. The philosophy is found in Preamble where a solemn resolve is made to secure to all its citizens, liberty of thought and expression.

In Collin’s Dictionary the word “Militant” is defined to describe people who believe in something very strongly and are active in trying to bring about political and social change, often in extreme ways that other people find unacceptable. The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967(UAPA) as amended, defines “Terrorist” in Section 15 as *“whosoever does any act with intent to threaten or likely to threaten the unity, integrity, security, economic security, or sovereignty of India ---“* which covers the restrictions imposed under Sub-clause(2) of Art. 19(1) .

In Writ Petition (Civil) No. 1031 Of 2019 Anuradha Bhasin ...Petitioner Versus Union Of India And Ors- Respondent and connected petitions, the Hon’ble Supreme Court laid down certain principles which the Govt has to follow to strike a balance between the freedom guaranteed by any of the sub clauses of clause 1) of Article 19 and the social control permitted by any of the clauses (2) to (6). The position that emerges is that the valuable and cherished right of freedom of expression and speech may at times have to be subjected to reasonable subordination to social interests, needs and necessities to preserve the very core of democratic life, preservation of public order and rule of law .

Any speech which incites imminent violence does not enjoy constitutional protection. However the doctrine of proportionality is enshrined in Article 19 itself which is an essential facet of the guarantee against arbitrary state action because it ensures that the nature and quality of the encroachment on the right is not

disproportionate to the purpose of the law . The phrase ‘reasonable restriction’ connotes that the limitation imposed on a person in enjoyment of the right should not be arbitrary or of an excessive nature , beyond what is required in the interests of the Public. The Order is subject to judicial review .

Various Laws have been enacted for curbing militancy. controlling law and order situation and internal Security viz for cross border terrorism in Jammu and Kashmir, insurgency related violence in some of the North, North Eastern (NE), Central and southern States and Naxal violence in several parts of the Country. The Schedule I to UAPA Act lists various Terrorist Organisations.

The adoption of a resolution on “freedom of opinion and expression” at the UN Human Rights Council was adopted on 16 June 2020. The resolution calls on States to “*ensure that all measures taken to counter threats related to terrorism and violent extremism are in full compliance with international human rights obligations, including the principles of lawfulness, legitimacy, necessity and proportionality*”.

However Human rights violations issues do crop up like arbitrary restrictions on freedom of expression and the press, unjustified arrests or prosecutions, use of criminal libel laws etc.

This article analyzes the interaction between judicial review evolving various doctrines viz. the Proportionality doctrine, the test of ‘direct impact’ as laid down in A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras, test of ‘direct and inevitable consequence’ as laid down in Rustom Cavasjee Cooper v. Union of India, widening the former test, Chilling effect concept (as in USA in the decision in Weiman v. Updgraff) etc. and state responses to militancy in India in the context of freedom of speech and expression.

Amnesty International calls for –“Your voice matters”- not to hate speech or other incitement to discrimination and violence but to speak out or protest peacefully.

Restriction –proportionate- reasonable – for preserving public order- National Security-Rule of Law .

1. INTRODUCTION

Roscoe Pound- “Law is the product of an inexorable mechanism of social forces.” After emerging from a grim battle against the British for recognition of the fundamental rights, the makers in the Constituent Assembly focussed on restrictions on freedom of speech and expression, as a means of safeguarding these rights in their pristine purity. The reason given was that we are faced, within our own society, with elements who misuse those rights. Hence limits were put on the operation of fundamental rights. Art. 19(1) (a) is limited in its scope by sub clause (2) as amended by the Constitution First Amendment Act (1951) with retrospective effect and (Sixteenth Amendment) Act, 1963. The philosophy is found in Preamble where a solemn resolve is made to secure to all its citizens, liberty of thought and expression.

In Collin’s Dictionary the word “Militant” is defined to describe people who believe in something very strongly and are active in trying to bring about political or social change, often in extreme ways that other people find unacceptable. The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967(UAPA) as amended, defines “Terrorist” in Section 15 as “*whosoever does any act with intent to threaten or likely to threaten the unity, integrity, security, economic security, or sovereignty of India --* “ which covers the restrictions imposed under Sub-clause(2) of Art. 19(1).

In Writ Petition (Civil) No. 1031 Of 2019 **Anuradha Bhasin ...Petitioner Versus Union Of India And Ors- Respondent and connected petitions**, the Petitioners challenged suspension of internet services in Jammu and Kashmir which has been a hotbed of terrorist insurgencies for many years .

The Hon'ble Supreme Court laid down certain principles which the Govt has to follow To strike a balance between the freedom guaranteed under Article 19(1) and the control under Article 19 (2) to 6. The position that emerges is that the valuable and cherished right of freedom of expression and speech may at times have to be subjected to reasonable subordination to social interests, needs and necessities to preserve the very core of democratic life, preservation of public order and rule of law.

Any speech which incites imminent violence does not enjoy constitutional protection. However the doctrine of proportionality, is enshrined in Article 19 itself which is an essential facet of the guarantee against arbitrary State action because it ensures that the nature and quality of the encroachment on the right is not disproportionate to the purpose of the law. The phrase "reasonable restriction" connotes that the limitation imposed on a person in enjoyment of the right should not be arbitrary or of an excessive nature, beyond what is required in the interests of the public.

Various Laws have been enacted for curbing militancy, controlling law and order situation and internal Security viz for cross border terrorism in Jammu and Kashmir, insurgency related violence in some of the North, North Eastern (NE), Central and southern States and Naxal violence in several parts of the Country. The Schedule I to UAPA Act lists various Terrorist Organisations. AFSPA is based on a 1942 British ordinance intended to contain the Indian Independence movement during the Second World War and was enacted by Independent India in the year 1958 by which powers were conferred upon the members of the armed forces in the areas under unrest in the State of Assam and the Union Territory of Manipur. By Act 7 of 1972 and Act 69 of 1986 the Central Act was amended and it extends to the whole of the State of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura. It was extended to Kashmir Region in the year 1990. Union Home Minister Mr. Amit Shah has stated on 31st March 2022 that areas under AFSPA are being reduced as a result of the improved security situation and fast-tracked development due to the consistent efforts and several agreements to end insurgency and bring lasting peace in North East by PM Narendra Modi government.

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This article analyzes the interaction between judicial review evolving various doctrines viz. the Proportionality doctrine, the test of 'direct impact' as laid down in **A.K. Gopalan v. State of Madras**, test of 'direct and inevitable consequence' as laid down in **Rustom Cavasjee Cooper v. Union of India**, widening the former test, Chilling effect concept (as in USA in the decision in **Weiman v. Updgraff**) etc. and state responses to militancy in India in the context of freedom of speech and expression.

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2. FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION – LIMITATIONS

"If liberty means anything at all, it means the right to tell people what they do not want to hear", words from George Orwell's proposed preface to *Animal Farm* (1945).¹

Freedom of speech and expression is understood to be fundamental in a democracy. One of the most notable proponents of the link between freedom of speech and democracy is Alexander

Meiklejohn (a political theorist, philosopher, president of Amherst College).ⁱⁱ [He (Alexander Meiklejohn) has argued that the concept of democracy is that of self-government by the people. For such a system to work, an informed electorate is necessary. In order to be appropriately knowledgeable, there must be no constraints on the free flow of information and ideas.]

However, censorship and control is deeply rooted in history for. e.g. in 1501, Pope Alexander VI issued a Bill against the unlicensed printing of books. In 1559, Pope Paul IV promulgated the Index Expurgatorius, or List of Prohibited Books.

England's Bill of Rights 1689 shortly after glorious revolution (the revolution of 1688-1689 in England which forcibly removed from power King James II and accession to the throne of his daughter Marry and her husband William)) legally established the constitutional right of freedom of speech in Parliament. One of the world's first freedom of the press Acts was introduced in Sweden in 1766, The Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen, adopted during the French Revolution in 1789, specifically affirmed freedom of speech as an inalienable right. Adopted in 1791, freedom of speech is a feature of the First Amendment to the United States Constitution. The French Declaration of the Rights of Man in 1789 mentions about freedom of expression in Article 11 as under –

“The free communication of ideas and opinions is one of the most precious of the rights of man. Every citizen may, accordingly, speak, write, and print with freedom, but shall be responsible for such abuses of this freedom as shall be defined by law.”

Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted in 1948, states that:

*“Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media and regardless of frontiers.”*ⁱⁱⁱ

The constitution of India was shaped by historical documents like Swaraj Bill 1895, The Commonwealth of India Bill 1925, Nehru Report 1928 Govt. Of India Act 1919, 1935; they included fundamental rights like freedom of expression, however these rights were subject to restrictions. In Commonwealth of India Bill 1925, under Section 7,

“the right of free expression of opinion was guaranteed for purposes not opposed to public order or morality, or the law relating to defamation for the time being”.

Section 124A in IPC relates to “Sedition” which was one of the restrictions imposed to restrict the right of freedom of speech and expression at pre constitution stage. During the debates in the Constituent Assembly, one member namely Sardar Bhopinder Singh Man (East Punjab: Sikh) had abhorred the word “Sedition” with the remark that Section 124A was specially framed for securing the conviction of Lokamanya Bal Gangadhar Tilak.^{iv}

Ultimately the Constitution finally framed and as amended contains Art 19(1) (a) – “All citizens shall have the right— (a) to freedom of speech and expression” --- 1[(2) Nothing in sub-clause (a) of clause (1) shall affect the operation of any existing law, or prevent the State from making any law, in so far as such law imposes reasonable restrictions on the exercise of the right conferred by the said sub-clause in the interests of 2[the sovereignty and integrity of India], the security of the State, friendly relations with foreign States, public order, decency or morality, or in relation to contempt of court, defamation or incitement to an offence.]. The philosophy is found in Preamble where a solemn resolve is made to secure to all its citizens, liberty of thought and expression. [Subs. by the Constitution (First Amendment) Act, 1951, s.

3, for cl. (2) (with retrospective effect). Ins. by the Constitution (Sixteenth Amendment) Act, 1963, s. 2 (w.e.f. 5-10-1963)].

3. LAWS IN INDIA FOR TACKLING MILITANCY

The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967 as amended in the Year 2004 (With Effect From 21-09-2004) was enacted to deal with terrorist activities. The First Schedule of the Act enumerates several terrorist organisations. The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Amendment Bill, 2019 was introduced in Lok Sabha by the Minister of Home Affairs, Mr. Amit Shah, on July 8, 2019. The Bill amends the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967. This amendment comprised the definition of “terrorist” to incorporate individuals under Sections 35 and 36 of the Act. The Act provides special procedures to deal with terrorist activities, among other things. The Bill additionally empowers the government to designate individuals as terrorists on the grounds mentioned therein. The Act defines terrorist acts to include acts committed within the scope of any of the treaties listed in the Second Schedule to the Act. The Second Schedule lists nine treaties. The Bill adds another treaty to the list. This is the International Convention for Suppression of Acts of Nuclear Terrorism (2005).

➤ **Official Secrets Act**

➤ “Unlawful activity” in UAPA Act is defined in Section 2(1) (o) interalia as “any action in relation to an individual or association, **by words, either spoken or written, or by signs or by visible representation or otherwise,---**” The said offences are related to the Defence of India and are covered by Entry 1 of the Union List.

➤ Section 15 of UAPA defines “terrorist act” The offence of terrorist act under Section 15 and the offence of unlawful activity under Section 2(1)(0) of the UAPA have some elements in commonality. The essential element in both is the challenge or threat or likely threat to the sovereignty, security, integrity and unity of India.

➤ *“UAPA does not tolerate dissent. It criminalises mere thoughts and political remonstrances that provoke disaffection with the State. Thus, it is an onslaught of citizens’ right to expression, a mutual right of groups and unions to propagate their views given under Article 19 of the Indian Constitution.--- In his speech in 1993, Atal Vihari Vajpayee apprehended that “the Government would declare all the opposition as unlawful.--- The Amendment dishonours the international conventions sanctioned by India. Especially legal principles under the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights and United Nations Special Rapporteur on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms.”^{vi}*

“After the November 26, 2008 terrorist attacks in Mumbai, the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967 was amended to become India’s main anti-terrorist law —.”

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➤ Armed Forces (Special Powers) Act (AFSPA), 1958 is an act of the Parliament of India that grants special powers to the Indian Armed Forces to maintain public order in "disturbed areas". According to the Disturbed Areas (Special Courts) Act, 1976 once declared 'disturbed', the area has to maintain status quo for a minimum of 6 months. Various Acts were promulgated under Art. 355 of the Constitution of India which confers power to the Central Government to protect every State from Internal disturbance. Govt’s declaration of an area as disturbed is not subject to Judicial review.

➤ Various Acts were enacted e.g. Armed Forces Special Powers (Assam and Manipur) Act, 1958 to curtail the activities of rebel Naga Nationalist Council (NNC). This Act

was expanded to the seven states of the North-East - Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Tripura, Arunachal Pradesh and Mizoram. In November 2016, Government of India has extended AFSPA in three districts of Arunachal Pradesh- Tirap, Changlang and Longding. These have been declared as "disturbed area" under Section 3 of the AFSPA.

- The Armed Forces (Punjab and Chandigarh) Special Powers Act, 1983 was withdrawn in 1997.
- The Armed Forces (Jammu and Kashmir) Special Powers Act, 1990
- Foreign Contribution Regulation (Amendment) Act, 2020 to Act of 2010. The Act prohibits foreign contribution for any activities, that pose a danger to national interest
- The Indian Penal Code, 1860 deals with offences and prescribes punishment .
- Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973.
- Instruments containing provision relevant to countering terrorist use of Internet:
 - South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation Regional Convention on Suppression of Terrorism (1987)
 - Arab Convention on the Suppression of Terrorism (1998)
 - Treaty on Cooperation among States Members of the Commonwealth of Independent States in Combating Terrorism (1999)
 - Convention of the Organization of the Islamic Conference on Combating International Terrorism (1999)
 - Organization of African Unity Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism (1999)
 - Inter-American Convention against Terrorism (2002)
 - Association of Southeast Asian Nations Convention on Counter Terrorism (2007)
 - Economic Community of West African States directive on fighting cybercrime (2009)

4. STATES AFFECTED BY MILITANCY

Cross-border terrorism in Jammu & Kashmir, Insurgent activities /Militant activities of various underground groups, ethnic divisions in several parts of the North East India, which comprises States of Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Tripura and Sikkim, naxal violence in 76 districts in 9 States of Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhatisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Orissa, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal are a cause for grave concern .^{vii}

Government of Assam vide letter dated 27/03/2024 extended AFSPA in “Disturbed Areas” (in Tinsukia, Dibrugarh; Charaideo; and Sivasagar) in the State of Assam for a further period of six months w.e.f. 01/04/2024”.^{viii}

The Central Govt. has further extended the AFSPA in three districts of Arunachal Pradesh, eight districts of Nagaland and some other areas for six more months with effect from 1/04/2024 .^{ix}

5. ACTIONS UNDER VARIOUS ANTITERRORISM ACTS IN THE RECENT PAST

- Cases were brought under sedition and terrorism laws, viz. caste-based violence in Bhima Koregaon in Maharashtra state in January 2018.
- National Safety Act (NSA) was used to make certain arrests in Uttar Pradesh.
- The Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act (UAPA) was used to make certain arrests.

- After the firing in Mon district on December 4, 2021 in which security forces gunned down 13 civilians., Nagaland Chief Minister Neiphiu Rio and Meghalaya Chief Minister Conrad Sangma have both called for repeal of AFSPA.^x

6. CASE LAWS WITH RESPECT TO FREEDOM OF SPEECH VIS-A-VIS , MILITANCY, MILITANT AFFECTED AREAS –JUDICIAL REVIEW

1. The Supreme Court vide its Judgment (2005) ended impunity of the Armed forces under AFSPA “It does not matter whether the victim was a common person or a militant or a terrorist, nor does it matter whether the aggressor was a common person or the state. The law is the same for both and is equally applicable to both... This is the requirement of a democracy and the requirement of preservation of the rule of law and the preservation of individual liberties,” a Bench of Justices Madan B. Lokur and U.U. Lalit said in an 85-page judgment.^{xi}

2. The Supreme Court Of India, Civil Original Jurisdiction Writ Petition (Civil) No. 1031 Of 2019 Anuradha Bhasin Versus Union Of India And Ors. And Writ Petition (Civil) No. 1164 Of 2019 Ghulam Nabi Azad Versus Union Of India And Anr.

As per advisory issued by Civil Secretariat , Home Department , Government of Jammu and Kashmir , on 4/08/2019 mobile phone networks , internet services , landline connectivity were all discontinued in the Kashmir valley, with restrictions on movement also being imposed in some areas. On 05/08/2019 Constitutional Order 272 was issued by the President applying all provisions of India to the State of Jammu and Kashmir and modifying Article 367 in its application to the State of Jammu and Kashmir. The Petitioners in Writ Petition (c) No. 1031 of 2019 claims that the movement of journalists in Srinagar was severely restricted and on 5/08/2019 , the Kashmir Times Srinagar Edition could not be distributed . The Petitioner has submitted that since 06/08/2019 she has been unable to publish the Srinagar edition of Kashmir Times pursuant to the aforesaid restrictions . The Petitioner further claimed that orders were not in compliance with the procedure prescribed under Temporary Suspension of Telecom Services (Public Emergency or Public Service) Rules 2017[hereinafter “Suspension Rules “].

The issues framed by the Court were –

- “*whether the freedom of speech and expression and freedom to practise any profession or to carry on any occupation , trade or business over the internet is a part of the fundamental rights under Part III of the Constitution ?*”
- *Whether the Government’s action of prohibiting internet access is valid?*
- *Whether the imposition of restrictions under Section 144,Cr.P.C. were valid?*
- *Whether the freedom of press of the Petitioner in Writ Petition (c) No. 1031 of 2019 was violated due to the restrictions ?*”

The Hon’ble Supreme Court enunciated the following principles which the govt. has to follow while imposing restrictions on fundamental rights of freedom of speech and expression in militant affected areas –

- “Article 19 of the Constitution has been interpreted to mandate **right to information** as an important fact of the right to freedom of speech and expression.
- Freedom of speech and expression includes the right to disseminate information (including through the medium of Internet)to as wide a section of the population as

possible . The wider range of circulation or its greater impact cannot restrict the content of the right nor can justify its denial.

- Restriction has also been held to include complete prohibition in appropriate cases.
- Three Propositions –
 - (i) Restriction on free speech and expression may include cases of prohibition.
 - (ii) There should not be excessive burden on free speech even if a complete prohibition is imposed and the government has to justify imposition of such prohibition and explain as to why lesser alternatives would be inadequate .
 - (iii) Whether a restriction amounts to a complete prohibition is a question of fact which is required to be determined by the Court with regard to the facts and circumstances of the case .

“There is no doubt that Jammu and Kashmir has been a hot bed of terrorist insurgencies for many years . In this light , we may note the State’s submission that since 1990 to 2019 there have been 32,71,038 recorded incidents of terrorist violence , 14,038 civilians have died , 5292 security personnel were martyred , 22,536 terrorists were killed . The geopolitical struggle cannot be played down or ignored .”

It is in this context, while the nation is facing such adversity ,an abrasive statement with imminent threat may be restricted , if the same impinges upon sovereignty and integrity of India . The question is one of extent rather than the existence of the power to restrict.

- “reasonable restrictions” are indispensable for the realisation of freedoms enshrined under Art. 19 ,as they are what ensure that enjoyment of rights is not arbitrary or excessive , so as to affect public interest .
- **The fundamental precepts of proportionality, as they emerge from decided cases can be formulated thus:**
 - A law interfering with fundamental rights must be in pursuance of a legitimate state aim.
 - The justification for rights infringing measures that interfere with or limit the exercise of fundamental rights and liberties must be based on the existence of a rational connection between those measures , the situation in fact and the object sought to be achieved .
 - The justification for rights infringing measures that interfere with or limit the exercise of fundamental rights and liberties must be based on existence of a rational connection between those measures , the situation in fact and the object sought to be achieved .
 - The measures must be necessary to achieve the object and must not infringe rights to an extent greater than is necessary to fulfil the aim .
 - Restrictions must not only serve legitimate purposes ; they must also be necessary to protect them ;and
 - The State must provide sufficient safeguards relating to the storing and protection of centrally stored data.
 - In a situation where fundamental rights of the citizens are being curtailed , the same cannot be done through an arbitrary exercise of Power ; rather it should be based on objective facts .
 - *“Chilling effect has been utilised in Indian Jurisprudence as a fairly recent concept ...the usage of the aforesaid principle is chiefly adopted for impugning an action of the State ,which may be constitutional but which imposes a great burden on the free speech. We may note that the argument of chilling effect, if not tempered judicially , would result in a “self proclaiming instrument .”*

- “Any order suspending internet under the Suspension Rules (Telegraph Act) is subject to judicial review based on the parameters set out herein .”
- While exercising the power under Section 144 Cr. P. C. , the Magistrate is duty bound to balance the rights and restrictions based on the principles of proportionality and thereafter apply the least intrusive measure .^{xii}

Kindly also refer to the following judgments -

[(**Ram Jethmalani v. Union of India**,(2011) 8 SCC1–“Petitioners seek the protection of fundamental rights , it is imperative that in such proceedings the Petitioners are denied the information necessary for them to properly articulate the case and be heard , especially where such information is in possession of the State.”)]

(Secretary , Ministry of Information and Broadcasting , Govt. of India Vs. Cricket Association of Bengal ,(1995) 2 SCC 161; Shreya Singhal Vs, Union of India (2015) 5 SCC 1- “ protection to the use of airwaves in the case of Secretary , Ministry of Information & Broadcasting , Government of India .”)

(Madhya Bharat Cotton Association Ltd. Vs. Union of India AIR 1954 SC 634, Narendra Kumar Vs. Union of India (1960) 2 SCR 375, State of Maharashtra Vs. Himmatbhai Narbheram Rao (1969) 2 SCR 392, Sushila Saw Mill Vs. State of Orissa (1995) 5 SCC 615, Pratap Pharma (Pvt.) Vs. Union of India (1997) 5 SCC 87 and Dharam Dutt Vs. Union of India (2004) 1 SCC 712 .)

(State of Gujrat Vs. Mirzapur Moti Kureshi Kassab Jamat (2005) 8 SCC 534)

(In Chintaman Rao Vs. State of Madhya Pradesh AIR 1951 SC 118 interpreted limitations on personal liberty and the balancing thereof as follows – “7. The phrase “reasonable restriction” connotes that the limitation imposed on a person in enjoyment of the right should not be arbitrary or of an excessive nature beyond what is required in the interests of the public.”

(Dr. Chandrachud , J. in the K.S. Puttaswamy (Aadhaar Case) reiterated the fundamental precepts of the doctrine of proportionality .]

3. Supreme Court of India in Union Of India vs K.A. Najeeb on 1 February, 2021 Author: Surya Kant Bench: N.V. Ramana, Surya Kant held_

“It is thus clear to us that the presence of statutory restrictions like Section 43–D (5) of UAPA per se does not oust the ability of Constitutional Courts to grant bail on grounds of violation of Part III of the Constitution. Indeed, both the restrictions under a Statute as well as the powers exercisable under Constitutional Jurisdiction can be well harmonised.”

4 Delhi High Court, Devangana Kalita Vs State Of NCT Delhi on 15 June, 2021 -Govt. allegations arise from protests, in which the appellant is alleged to have participated, against the Citizenship Amendment Act, 2019 ('CAA', for short) passed by Parliament and the exercise undertaken by the Central Government to create a database of citizens called the National Register of Citizens ('NRC', for short)[including whatsapp chat etc.] ; and the gravamen of the allegation is that as part of such protests, the appellant along with co-conspirators instigated the local population in certain Muslim dominated areas of Delhi, particularly women, and incited in them feelings of persecution, which subsequently led to violence and rioting.

The Hon'ble Court held –

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“ 47. We are afraid, that in our opinion, shorn-off the superfluous verbiage, hyperbole and the stretched inferences drawn from them by the prosecuting agency, the factual allegations made against the appellant do not prima facie disclose the commission of any offence under sections 15, 17 and/or 18 of the UAPA. As expatiated by the Hon'ble Supreme Court in the precedents cited above, protests against Governmental and Parliamentary actions are legitimate; and though such protests are expected to be peaceful and non-violent, it is not uncommon for protesters to push the limits permissible in law. The making of inflammatory speeches, organising chakkajams, and such like actions are not uncommon when there is widespread opposition to Governmental or Parliamentary actions. Even if we assume for the sake of argument, without expressing any view thereon, that in the present case inflammatory speeches, chakkajams, instigation of women protesters and **other crossed the line of peaceful protests permissible under our Constitutional guarantee, that however would yet not amount to commission of a 'terrorist act' or a 'conspiracy' or an 'act preparatory' to the commission of a terrorist act as understood under the UAPA.**”

The Delhi High Court granted bail to Pinjra Tod activists Devangana Kalita and Natasha Narwal, and also to Jamia Milia Islamia student Asif Iqbal Tanha, who were arrested under stringent anti-terror law UAPA.

The Hon'ble Court has also stated, “ 48. We are constrained to say, that it appears, that in its anxiety to suppress dissent and in the morbid fear that matters may get out of hand, **the State has blurred the line between the constitutionally guaranteed 'right to protest' and 'terrorist activity'. If such blurring gains traction, democracy would be in peril.**”. “33. Upon a careful consideration of the aforesaid verdicts of the Hon'ble Supreme Court, in our opinion, the intent and purpose of Parliament in enacting the UAPA and in amending it in 2004 and 2008 to bring terrorist activity within its scope, was and could only have been, to deal with matters of profound impact on the 'Defence of India', nothing more and nothing less. Had that not been the case, UAPA could not have been enacted by Parliament since the only entries in List-I of the Seventh Schedule to the Constitution with Entry 93 relating to the Defence of India and offences with respect to the Defence of India. It was not the intent, nor purpose of enacting UAPA that other offences of the usual and ordinary kind, however grave, egregious or heinous in their nature and extent, should also be covered by UAPA, since such conventional matters would have fallen within Entry 1 of List-II (State List) and/or Entry 1 of List-III (Concurrent List) of the Seventh Schedule of our Constitution. This is the only possible view that can be taken if we are to lean in favour of constitutionality of the provisions of section 15, 17 and 18 of the UAPA, as that would bring the statute within the legislative competence of Parliament are Entry 1 read we must.”(**Delhi High Court, Devangana Kalita vs State Of NCT Delhi on 15 June, 2021**)^{xiii}

5 . Supreme Court of India

Naga People's Movement, Of Human ... vs Union Of India on 27 November, 1997

Author: S Agrawal, Bench: Cji, M.M. Punchhi, S.C. Agarwal, A.S. Anand, S.P. Bharucha,

The writ petitions and appeals raised common questions relating to the validity of the Armed Forces (Special Powers) Act, 1958 (as amended) enacted by Parliament (hereinafter referred to as 'the Central Act') and the Assam Disturbed Areas Act, 1955 enacted by the State Legislature of Assam. (hereinafter referred to as 'the State Act').

The Hon'ble Supreme Court arrived at the following conclusions –

“(1) Parliament was competent to enact the Central Act in exercise of the legislative power conferred on it under Entry 2 of List I and Article 248 read with Entry 97 of the List I . After the insertion of Entry 2A in List I by the Forty Second Amendment to the Constitution, the legislative power of the Parliament to enact the Central Act flows from Entry 2A of List I . It is not a law in respect of maintenance of public order falling under Entry I of List II .”

(2) The expression "in aid of the civil power" in Entry 2A of List I and in Entry 1 of List II implies that deployment of the armed forces of the Union shall be for the purpose of enabling the civil power in the State to deal with the situation affecting maintenance of public order which has necessitated the deployment of the armed forces in the State.

...(4) The armed forces of the Union would operate in the State concerned in co-operation with the civil administration so that the situation which has necessitated the deployment of armed forces is effectively dealt with and normalcy is restored. ...

6) The Central Act cannot be regarded as a colourable legislation or a fraud on the Constitution. it is not a measure intended to achieve the same result as contemplated by a Proclamation of Emergency under Article 352 or a proclamation under Article 356 of the Constitution.

(7) Section 3 of the Central Act does not confer an arbitrary or unguided power to declare an area as a "disturbed area" .

(8) A declaration under Section 3 has to be for a limited duration and there should be periodic review of the declaration before the expiry of six months.

(9) ... it is desirable that the State Government should be consulted by the Central Government while making the declaration....

(11) The conferment of the power to make a declaration under Section 3 of the Central Act on the Central Government is not violative of the federal scheme as envisaged by the Constitution

... (13) **The Powers conferred under clauses (a) to (d) of Section 4 and Section 5 of the Central Act on the officers of the armed forces, including a on- Commissioned Officer are not arbitrary and unreasonable and are not violative of the provisions of Articles 14, 19 or 21 of the Constitution.**

(14) While exercising the powers conferred under Section 4(a) of the Central Act, the officer in the armed forces shall use minimal force required for effective action against the person/persons acting in contravention of the prohibitory order.

(15) A person arrested and taken into custody in exercise of the powers under Section 4(c) of the Central Act should be handed over to the officer-in-charge of the nearest police station with least possible delay so that he can be produced before nearest magistrate within 24 hours of such arrest excluding the time taken for journey from the place of arrest to the court of magistrate.

...(18) Section 6 of the Central Act in so far as it confers a discretion on the Central Government to grant or refuse sanction for instituting prosecution or a suit or proceeding against any person -- does not suffer from the vice of arbitrariness. Since the order of the Central Government refusing or granting the sanction under Section 6 is subject to judicial review, the Central Government shall pass an order giving reasons.

(19) While exercising the powers conferred under clauses (a) to (d) of Section 4 the officers of the armed forces shall strictly follow the instructions contained in the list of "Do's and Don'ts" issued by the army authorities which are binding and any disregard to the said instructions would entail suitable action under the Army Act, 1950.

(20) The instructions contained in the list of "Do's and Don'ts " shall be suitably amended so as to bring them in conformity with the guidelines contained in the decisions of this Court and to incorporate the safeguards that are contained in clauses (a) to (d) of Section 4 and Section

5 of the Central Act as construed and also the direction contained in the order of this Court dated July 4, 1991 in Civil Appeal No. 2551 of 1991.

(21) A complaint containing an allegation about misuse or abuse of the powers conferred under the Central Act shall be thoroughly inquired into and, if on enquiry it is found that the allegations are correct, the victim should be suitably compensated and the necessary sanction for institution of prosecution and/or a suit or other proceeding should be granted under Section 6 of the Central Act.

(22) The State Act is, in pith and substance, a law in respect of maintenance of public order enacted in exercise of the legislative power conferred on the State Legislature under Entry 1 of List II....

(24) The rest of the provisions of Sections 4 and 5 of the State Act are not open to challenge under Article 254 of the Constitution on the ground of repugnance to the provisions contained in Cr.P.C. and the Arms Act.

(25) The considerations governing the exercise of the powers conferred under Sections 3 to 6 of the Central Act indicated above will also apply to exercise of powers conferred under Sections 3 to 6 of the State Act. ^{xiv}

6. In 2016, a bench of Justices Madan Lokur and U U Lalit on fake encounters in Manipur held-

“The law is very clear that if an offence is committed even by Army personnel, there is no concept of absolute immunity from trial by the criminal court constituted under the Criminal Procedure Code,” the Court said.

The Judgment also called for a probe into alleged 1,528 cases extra-judicial killings by security forces in Manipur during 2000-12. ^{xv}

7. VARIOUS REFORMATIVE STEPS

- The Inter-State Council was established under article 263 of the Constitution of India through a Presidential Order dated the May 28, 1990.
- The Zonal Councils, five in number, have been set up under the States Re-organisation Act, 1956.
- The Government of India had enacted the Protection of Human Rights Act in 1993 whereby the National Human Rights Commission was established primarily in order to enquire into complaints of human rights violations and suggest appropriate measures for promotion and protection of Human Rights in this country.
- **Justice Jeevan Reddy Commission**
The commission recommended repealing AFSPA as "the Act is a symbol of hate, oppression, and instrument of high-handedness". It had submitted its report on 06.06.2005. ^{xvi}
- **Second Administrative Reforms Commission**
▶ The second Administratively Reforms Commission (ARC) in its fifth report on "Public Order", recommended to repeal of Armed Forces Special Powers Act, 1958.. The commission recommended to amend the Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act, 1967 inserting a new chapter to deploy the armed forces of the Union in the North eastern States. ^{xvii}

These draconian laws are based on the concept that they protect an impending threat to the sovereignty and integrity of India and threat to Security of the State . However excess powers tear the very fabric of fundamental rights .

Lord Chancellor of the United Kingdom, Lord Falconer, observed in 2006: “... Courts are not conducting the fight against terrorism. Nor are they deciding the measures to be used. The level of threat, and the extent to which exceptional measures are required, are for the executive, or the legislature. The questions the courts in the UK ask are: first, do these measures infringe any individual's fundamental human rights; second if they do, is there a justification for the infringement; and third, is the infringement the minimum necessary to protect our democracy? ”

CONCLUSION

1. Freedom of Expression may be restricted under the conditions defined by article 19 (2); the fundamental test is that of proportionality.
2. Those charged with terrorist Acts must have their guilt or innocence determined in the judicial Review.
3. Notifications issued various antiterrorism Acts should be for a limited period and there should be a periodic review to ascertain whether they should be continued.
4. In case of misuse or abuse of the Powers by the Govt. under various antiterrorism Acts resulting in human right violations , there should be access to an effective remedy, which may, depending on the damage suffered, include compensation.
5. As laid down by verdicts of the Hon'ble Supreme Court, the intent and purpose of Parliament in enacting the UAPA and in amending it to bring terrorist activity within its scope, was and could only have been, to deal with matters of profound impact on the 'Defence of India', nothing more and nothing less; it follows that that utilisation of power by govt. should be limited to such matters only.^{xviii}
6. As warned by the Hon'ble Court **Devangana Kalita vs State Of Nct Delhi** there **should not be** the frivolous invocation of the “extremely grave and serious penal provisions” under UAPA, as such a proposition “*would undermine the intent and purpose of the Parliament in enacting a law that is meant to address threats to the very existence of our nation*“.^{xix}
7. The requisite sanction under Section 6 of the Central Act (AFSPA) should be granted by the State for institution of prosecution and/or a civil suit or other proceeding against the person/persons responsible for such violation.
8. The Judiciary shall protect individual rights and freedoms and promote constitutional values not as a discretion but as an obligation.
9. Effective counter-terrorism measures and the protection of human rights are complementary, symbiotic and mutually strengthening objectives which must be pursued together.

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